

2022

ARCUS

ARCTIC RESEARCH CONSORTIUM
OF THE UNITED STATES

ANNUAL MEETING REPORT

TUESDAY, 1 NOVEMBER 2022

PHOTO BY ADEENA TERES (POLARTRES 2017)

I. INTRODUCTION

The Arctic Research Consortium of the US (ARCUS) is a US 501(c)(3) not-for-profit organization that serves the Arctic research community. ARCUS envisions strong and productive connections among US and international Arctic researchers, educators, Indigenous and Traditional Knowledge holders, Arctic residents and local experts, and other stakeholders to improve understanding of the changing Arctic. Membership is open to all organizations and individuals engaged in Arctic research or stakeholders to it, including academic, research, government, Indigenous, and corporations. In 2022, thirty institutions and 142 individual members were part of the ARCUS membership community committed to building and sustaining the extended network of collaborative relationships that enable Arctic research.

ARCUS has held an Annual Meeting nearly every year since its inception in 1988. This open community meeting serves as an important opportunity for the ARCUS Board of Directors and staff to connect with ARCUS members, partners, and others from the wider Arctic research community around key Arctic research and education issues and collaboration opportunities.

"Thank you for keeping this open to non-members. Even with all the other Arctic networks, ARCUS still occupies a unique space."

The 2022 ARCUS Annual Meeting was held virtually on Tuesday, 1 November 2022. The meeting brought together 120 individuals from the Arctic research community, including 40 attendees from ARCUS member institutions and 19 ARCUS individual members. 80% of ARCUS' member institutions participated in the event—either through meeting attendance or through the submission of institutional member presentations or reports.

The goals of the 2022 ARCUS Annual Meeting were to:

1. **CONNECT:** Bring members of the Arctic research and education community together to meet, talk, and connect.
2. **SHARE:** Explore what individuals and organizations are doing to address key challenges and opportunities.
3. **ADVANCE:** Identify actionable ways to work together and support each other.

II. MEETING OVERVIEW & SMALL GROUP DISCUSSION SUMMARIES

The structure of the 2022 meeting agenda emphasized small group discussions to encourage relationship development and exchange among ARCUS members and other meeting participants. To maximize discussion time during the brief three-hour virtual event, ARCUS staff updates were kept to a minimum. A [pre-recorded ARCUS overview presentation](#) from ARCUS' Executive Director Helen Wiggins, ARCUS Membership Committee Chair Adrian Gall, and ARCUS Membership Committee Vice-Chair Stacey Fritz was shared in advance of the meeting. Additional information about ARCUS FY22 financials, programs, and activities were provided to members in the [ARCUS 2022 Annual Report](#) distributed via email in December 2022 and published to the ARCUS website.

The remainder of this report summarizes meeting discussion themes and provides a brief synopsis of the small group conversations. A number of criteria informed the Annual Meeting Planning Committee's 2022 theme selection. Themes were intended to be broad enough to allow for meeting participants with a wide diversity of community interest and experience to contribute. They built on ARCUS Strategic Goal priorities, disseminated and advanced ideas generated through prior ARCUS meetings or committee reports, and aimed to leverage the expertise and interests of ARCUS Board, Member Representatives, and committee volunteers. Selected themes also provided an opportunity to explore potential partnerships and focus areas for future programming or ARCUS member committees and working groups.

The 2022 Annual Meeting discussion themes were:

Exploring ARCUS Member Goals, Activities, & Expertise – an opportunity for ARCUS members to highlight their organizations, research activities, collaboration interests, and expertise.

Utilizing Indigenous Co-Production of Knowledge Frameworks & Supportive Practices – solutions that help address research co-production challenges and opportunities for expanding the appropriate use of co-production frameworks & supportive practices in collaborative research activities.

Identifying Supports for International Collaborations – current policies, projects, organizations, and funding mechanisms enabling international collaboration and/or mitigating current disruptions to international Arctic research activities (e.g., COVID-19 pandemic, war in Ukraine).

Promoting Alignment & Connections Across Arctic Research Networks – alignment needs and opportunities among the growing number of Arctic research networks represented by members of the ARCUS community.

Bridging Alaskan & North Atlantic Arctic Research Agendas – collaboration opportunities and ideas for a shared research agenda between experts representing the Arctic research interests and assets of Alaska and the North Atlantic.

Exploring ARCUS Member Goals, Activities, & Expertise

In preparation for the Annual Meeting, ARCUS institutional members were invited to submit [written and pre-recorded updates](#) on the Arctic research activities within their organizations. Member representatives were also invited to present organizational updates orally as part of two breakout groups focused on sharing and discussing member goals, activities, and expertise.

"The meeting was a great opportunity to learn about various organizations and current research being conducted on Inuit Nunaat."

2022 ARCUS Institutional Members

Reports or presentations were shared by the following institutional members:

- **Alaska Ocean Observing System**, shared by Sheyna Wisdom
- **Arctic Centre, Ulapland**, shared by Stephan Kircher
- **Arizona State University**, shared by Masha Monakhova
- **Kawerak, Inc.**, shared by Julie Raymond-Yakoubian
- **University of the Arctic**, shared by Kirsi Latola
- **ABR, Inc.**, shared by Adrian Gall
- **Dartmouth College**, shared by Melody Brown Burkins
- **National Renewable Energy Laboratory**, shared by Stacey Fritz
- **Norwegian Polar Institute**, shared by Nalân Koç
- **Sandia National Laboratories**, shared by Mark Ivey
- **Sitka Sound Science Center**, shared by Alex McCarrel
- **The George Washington University**, shared by Robert Orttung
- **University of Alaska Anchorage**, shared by Diane Hirshberg
- **University of Alaska Fairbanks**, shared by Peter Webley
- **University of Alaska Southeast**, shared by Charmaine Robinson
- **University of Maine**, shared by Pips Veazey
- **University of Northern British Columbia**, shared by Gary Wilson
- **University of Southern Maine**, shared by Ross Hickey and Tracey Meagher
- **University of Virginia**, shared by Howard Epstein
- **US Permafrost Association**, shared by John Thornley
- **WWF US Arctic Program**, shared by Alexis Will
- **University of Washington**, shared by Edward Blanchard-Wrigglesworth and Craig Lee

Links to the report documents and recorded presentation have been archived and remain available on the [ARCUS 2022 Annual Meeting website](#) and [ARCUS YouTube channel](#).

Utilizing Indigenous Co-Production of Knowledge Framework & Supportive Practices

Two breakout groups at the 2022 ARCUS Annual Meeting were dedicated to the theme, Utilizing Indigenous Co-Production of Knowledge Frameworks & Supportive Practices. The goal of these groups was to highlight solutions that help address research co-production challenges and explore opportunities for expanding the appropriate use of co-production frameworks and supportive practices in collaborative research activities.

The first breakout group began their discussion by identifying a shared definition of Indigenous co-production of knowledge:

"a process that brings together Indigenous Peoples' knowledge systems and science to generate new knowledge and understandings of the world that would likely not be achieved through the application of only one knowledge system. CPK emphasizes the importance of attaining equity in research relationships. ... CPK is the process of bringing together two different knowledge systems, in true partnership and equity, to enhance, learn, and create new understandings on a specific topic."

Source: Ellam Yua, J. Raymond-Yakoubian, R. Aluaq Daniel, and C. Behe. 2021. Negeqlikacarni Kangingnaulriani Ayuqenrilnguut Piyaraitgun Kangingnauryararkat: A Framework for Co-Production of Knowledge in the Context of Arctic Research. *Ecology and Society* 27(1):34 <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12960-270134>.

"I loved the incredibly welcome approach, strong facilitators, & excellent dissemination of resources."

What CPK experience exists within this small group?	Answer in green, please. If you're comfortable, please include your name on your post-it.	I do not have any CPK experience. Looking forward to listening to discussions and learning.	No specific Arctic Experience , but Indigenous culture co-production experience in the pac. islands and with fishing comm. Hope to learn about unique aspects of Arctic CPK	What are the specific CPK interests (challenges and solutions) of the people in this group?	I am working on creating guides for community partners (rather than researchers) to empower communities via Arctic research. Looking for topics!	A key challenge is setting up research through formal agreements, such as MOUs. This is really important takes lots of discussion and preliminary work.
I collaborate with Inuit in Nunavut to develop projects, conduct research, and share research results to address their priorities.e.g shipping, safe travel, harvesting.	SIKU: the Indigenous Knowledge Social Network, designed by and for Inuit & Indigenous, is a tool for people to make posts about their observations, and has project mgt options	No experience yet, but I now work with a group of people who have done so for years, so I am learning a lot. I am eager to learn about CPK for design/architecture/re silience.	I'm working on a project that aspires to braid Indigenous science with Western engineering in the context of flood mitigation and climate adaptation.	It is really important to meet face-to-face to establish relationships. I have done this with small seed grants to get the relationship in place to partner on a larger grant.	Finding partner communities	Another priority is data archiving and access
Not experienced with Arctic communities yet. Experience with Andean Quechua and Aymara farmers co-production on how IK is produce and its inequalities	Community partners are needed for co-produced knowledge. Community needs, interest, and capacity.	I study equitable community engagement (Inuit communities in particular) and present on it regularly. I also use this framework in my work.	The Arctic Studies Center also works with Alaska Native artists to produce media pieces on their work in traditional forms such as seal intestine garments, grass basketry, etc.	Institutional barriers such as research ethics and financial systems, that can delay/inhibit community-driven research/co-production of knowledge.	How to analyze data from academia and communities collaboratively for final products/publications.	We have hosted one collaborative analysis workshop for our project (last fall) and are hosting another later this month. I could share (later) our agenda and some ideas if of interest. Nat
One aspect is CPK in collaboration with Yakutat Tlingit Tribe on ecological and historical knowledge about Yakutat fiord. Co-researchers were community scholars and elders.	I have read lots of CPK reports/papers/resources and facilitated meetings, but never participated in a CPK project from start to finish	Documented Yup'ik place names, associated stories, and these locations on the map with Iliamna Lake Yup'ik Elders.	I work w/ NSF Arctic Research Support & am the Exec. Sec. for the Bering Task Force working with the Tribal Advisory Council, excited to learn more about CPK!	Funding/support to co-develop proposals (and build relationships with those we are co-producing knowledge with). SSHRC does \$25k to help with at LOI stage		

Small Group Relational Introductions to Indigenous Co-Production of Knowledge Topics

The second group began their session with relational introductions by individually sharing what personal experiences they had with co-production of knowledge. Answers ranged from none-at-all to strong expertise, and allowed the group to proceed through the discussion prompts with a good understanding of each other's experiences.

Ways to move beyond challenges to co-production were discussed by both groups. The first group focused on the following co-production issues:

- Scientists bringing communities into research projects after the research topic has been identified;
- funders encouraging community involvement in research and overwhelming communities with research participation requests;
- false claims of co-production; and
- more time in villages needed for scientists.

The second group structured their conversation around the types of challenges outlined in the ARCUS [Understanding and Overcoming Collaborative Arctic Research Challenges report](#).

Research Conceptualization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan for relationship-building to take a year or more • Spend time in the communities to build connections to the land & people, avoid being a "snowbird" • Hire someone from the community to be your guide • Connect with non-profit Indigenous groups as a way to better understand community needs • Establish community relationships through partners who might be better connected • Shift how outreach efforts are viewed away from a personal/institutional economic benefit lens (e.g., pursuit of project funding) to a relationship/trust-building lens • Identify community priorities first, then find money
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Proposal Preparation & Submission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow time, secure funding for meeting in-person to do this • Find a balance between addressing community priorities & ensuring scientific rigor to ensure strong evidence is documented/collected • Incorporate a community research review processes in project development and review plans
Collaboration Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have a community meeting every time researcher(s) visit the community, sharing project previous outcomes and progress • Attend/participate in meetings or events where community partners are already present (i.e., rather than starting new meetings) • Project example: Aron Crowell’s cultural ecoscape project at Yakutat had a multiparty MOA prepared under the National Historic Preservation Act & included agreements for oral & archaeological data
Plan Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIKU (www.siku.org) is a tool designed to facilitate Indigenous-led solutions, helps Inuit make & manage observations, & provides researchers with a framework for managing observations • Meet with partners often to touch base about progress & how the methods (decision-making & actions) have been going, adjust as needed
Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research reports should be community reviewed before publication • Evaluate all through the project, not just at the end, & adjust accordingly • Have all team members participate in evaluation activities to ensure everyone has a say, all voices must be treated equally • Empower Indigenous communities and research reviewers to be able to call out researchers doing CPK inappropriately (e.g., inadequate levels of involvement, tokenizing, false claims of CPK)
Translation/Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community knowledge will be orally conveyed by participating knowledge holders & a detailed plan for inviting, recording, transcribing interviews is needed • Others can see & learn from posts and projects on SIKU (with the appropriate privacy/stewardship options) • All interviews must have an informed consent agreement, right of review, IRB clearance

Useful CPK references shared by the group included:

- Ellam Yua, J. Raymond-Yakoubian, R. A. Daniel, and C. Behe. 2022. A Framework for Co-production of Knowledge in the Context of Arctic Research. *Negeqlikacaarni Kangingnaulriani Ayuqenrilnguut Piyaraitgun Kangingnauryararkat. Ecology and Society* 27(1): 34. <https://ecologyandsociety.org/vol27/iss1/art34/>
- Kawerak, Inc. 2021. Knowledge and Research Sovereignty Workshop, May 18–21, 2021 Workshop Report. Prepared by Sandhill.Culture.Craft and Kawerak Inc. Social Science Program. Nome, Alaska. <https://kawerak.org/download/kawerak-knowledge-and-research-sovereignty-ksi-workshop-report/>
- Northern Communities Strategic Document Synthesis Narrative. 2020. IARPC Collaborations. 16 August 2020. 21 pp. https://www.iarpcollaborations.org/uploads/cms/documents/northern_communities_document_synthesis.pdf
- NNA-CO <https://nna-co.org/strategic-objectives/co-production-knowledge>
- ARCUS Conducting Research with Northern Communities page is a compilation of resources throughout the Arctic - <https://www.arcus.org/resources/northern-communities>
- K.J. Wilson, T. Bell, A. Arreak, B. Koonoo, D. Angnatsiak, and G. J. Ljubicic. 2020. Changing the role of non-Indigenous research partners in practice to support Inuit self-determination in research Lessons learned from a non-Indigenous researcher on co-production. *Arctic Science* 6: 127–153. - <https://cdnsiencepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1139/as-2019-0021>
- Heather Sauyaq Jean Gordon. 2017. Building Relationships in the Arctic: Indigenous Communities and Scientists in *Northern Sustainabilities: Understanding and Addressing Change in the Circumpolar World*. Editors: G. Fondahl and G. N. Wilson. Springer, 357 pp. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-46150-2_18](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-46150-2_18)
- Recorded Presentation: [Indigenous Evaluation: How to Engage with Indigenous Tribes & Communities in Evaluation Research](#)
- Inuit Circumpolar Council. 2022. Circumpolar Inuit Protocols for Ethical and Equitable Engagement. <https://iccalaska.org/wp-icc/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/EEE-Protocols-LR-1.pdf>
- Nina Nikola Doering, et al. 2022. Improving the Relationships Between Indigenous Rights Holders and Researchers in the Arctic: An Invitation for Change in Funding and Collaboration. *Environmental Research Letters* 17. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/ac72b5>
- Website: [Kawerak Social Sciences Program](#)
- Recorded Presentation: [Different Ways of Knowing: Successful Examples of Co-production of Knowledge in Arctic research](#)

- Kawerak, Inc. web resource related to equity in CPK partnerships: <https://kawerak.org/knowledge-sovereignty-and-the-indigenization-of-knowledge-2/>
- Carter, N. A., J. Dawson, N. Simonee, S. Tagalik, and G. Ljubicic. 2019. Lessons Learned Through Research Partnership with Inuit. *Arctic* 72: 337–484. <https://journalhosting.ucalgary.ca/index.php/arctic/article/view/69507>
- This paper shows a range of participatory research: David-Chavez, D. M. and M. C. Gavin 2018. A Global Assessment of Indigenous Community Engagement in Climate Research. *Environmental Research Letters* 13. Retrieved from: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/aaf300> However, true co-production of knowledge is only on the far right, true equality and equity is the requirement for CPK
- These two letters talk about issues with ethical research in the Arctic, letters to NSF Navigating the New Arctic: <https://kawerak.org/download/navigating-the-new-arctic-program-comment-letter/> and <https://kawerak.org/download/dec-2021-nna-follow-up-letter/>
- An example of incorporating Indigenous Knowledge in fisheries management: <https://kawerak.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/The-incorporation-of-traditional-knowledge-into-Alaska-federal-fisheries-management.pdf>
- M. Wagner. Reciprocity and Respect: Learning Methodologies for Indigenous Research. Web-based article at Indigenous Aquaculture, accessed 13 January 2022 - <https://indigenouaquaculture.org/ceremony-relationships-reciprocity-and-respect-learning-methodologies-for-indigenous-research/communities>.

Identifying Supports for International Collaborations

The goal of the *Identifying Supports for International Collaborations* discussion theme was to exchange ideas about mechanisms to enable international collaboration and mitigate current disruptions to international Arctic research activities. This theme was also addressed by two breakout groups.

Both groups acknowledged the range of networks, conferences, intergovernmental agreements, and funding mechanisms that exist to support international Arctic research collaboration as well as the difficulties that both the COVID-19 pandemic and war in Ukraine currently present to international exchange. Instability has hampered collaboration and many international Arctic projects and research collaborations are currently on hold. However, despite these challenges and the notable pause to Arctic Council activities, a number of avenues remain open for international collaboration.

The groups made the following recommendations for strengthening these connections:

- Researchers interested in international exchange were encouraged to take part in diplomatic opportunities such as the Fulbright program, which still remains active.
- Researchers and students were encouraged to learn more about the numerous University of the Arctic mechanisms designed for both researchers and students. Examples:

- UArctic's institutes & thematic networks; UArctic course participation enabled through the North2North exchange program; and the next UArctic Congress (29 May–2 June 2024 in Bodø, Norway).
- Group members agreed that a more widely publicized directory of both US and international programs and funding sources that help to enable international travel, meetings, relationship development, and collaborative research projects would be a helpful community resource.
- A library of program policy examples and agreements that enable faculty and student exchanges from a variety of organizations was also seen as a useful resource to develop.
- A recommendation was made to establish a forum to bring national Arctic research organizations such as ARCUS and the Association of Canadian Universities for Northern Studies (ACUNS) together around major annual conferences (e.g., the Arctic Circle Assembly). Group members also encouraged these type of organizations to play a more active and collaborative role as:
 - coordinators for visiting scholar programs and administrators for travel awards.
 - evangelists working together to expand international awareness of their affiliated national and regional Arctic research capabilities and assets.
- The need to be inclusive of non-academic perspectives in international Arctic research exchange as well as the important role that the education process plays in enabling inclusive research and collaboration around major international issues was also emphasized.

PHOTO BY JON PAZOL (POLARTREC 2021)

Promoting Alignment & Connections Across Arctic Research Networks

Two of the meeting's breakout groups discussed ideas for encouraging greater connectivity across the growing number of Arctic research networks. Both groups agreed that existing web resources and collaboration platforms for Arctic researchers are not yet recognized as entirely meeting the desire and need for a central and accessible location where diverse Arctic researchers feel welcome to ask for and offer help with Arctic data and collaborative research projects. Although different organizations do host various tools and resources partially designed to support these activities, no one tool is yet perceived as being the "go to" place where new and established researchers or others interested in Arctic research can:

- Find topic areas that are directly relevant to their interests;
- discover researchers and institutions working on key questions facing the Arctic world; and
- openly join and participate with others in these collaborative efforts.

Rather than creating and maintaining separate tools and platforms, multiple Arctic research communities and networks may benefit from coming together to link existing resources and/or to jointly contribute content and facilitation support to a central Arctic research community hub.

Different example components or models for potential online hub integration include:

- Scott Polar Research Institute's Polar Directory for organizations involved in Polar Research: <https://www.spri.cam.ac.uk/resources/directory/>
- ARCUS Directory of Arctic Researchers to help identify potential research collaborators: <https://www.arcus.org/researchers>
- ARCUS Arctic Calendar to help identify community meetings and events.
- UArctic Thematic Networks as an example of bottom-up approach to the organization of research collaboration groups: <https://www.uarctic.org/activities/thematic-networks/>
- IARPC Collaborations as an example of "top-down" approaches to the organization of research collaboration groups: <https://www.iarpccollaborations.org/index.html>
- Arctic Data Center as an example of a centralized portal for acquisition and use of Arctic data: <https://arcticdata.io/catalog/data>
- ARCUS listservs and newsletters as examples of widely subscribed tools that users can use to share community news and engage with other members: <https://www.arcus.org/mailling-lists>
- Examples of collaboration policies and best practices for both in-person and virtual team or meeting facilitation.

"It is helpful to have an opportunity to talk about these questions in interdisciplinary groups."

PHOTO BY IGNATIUS RIGOR, COURTESY OF SARAH R. JOHNSON (POLARTREC 2022)

There is widespread interest in informational materials or "networking products" that help make sense of the complex and growing Arctic research sector. Updates or expansions of past efforts to map the US Arctic research sector (examples: [Cheryl Rosa's 2012 Arctic Org Chart Prezi](#), [UW Libraries Arctic & Northern Studies Research Guide](#), [NOAA PMEL's Arctic Zone](#), or the [Isaffik Arctic Gateway](#)) could be tied into collaboration hubs to enable greater cross-network awareness. These products would greatly benefit both established researchers as well as those new to the Arctic and could serve as an immediate benefit capable of drawing a variety of individuals, institutions, and networks into the shared workspace.

The discussion groups cautioned any new efforts to organize or implement integrated workspace solutions to:

- Partner with & avoid duplicating the efforts of other organizations.
- Make online resources mobile friendly.
- Consider ways to incorporate "fun" or "gaming" aspects into the content.
- Ensure potential users or target audiences can identify the value-added services that will benefit them from the very beginning.
- Make data portals more friendly for educators and non-expert users (this may require users to provide more accessible metadata).
- Be very thoughtful in advance about who this will be for, how people will be convinced to use the tool, what real benefits it will provide, appropriate levels of detail needed, and the huge time commitment that will likely be needed.

A number of ideas were also discussed by both breakout groups as possible ways to enhance Arctic research connectivity through better alignment of meetings and events. Participants called on meeting organizers to do more to pay attention to and connect with other convening organizations to survey the wider landscape of upcoming events. Researchers were encouraged to attend events like the Alaska Federation of Natives or the Alaska Forum on the Environment as ways to network with and learn more about issues facing Alaska's Indigenous communities. Conveners were also encouraged to experiment with using alternate online gathering spaces (e.g., Reddit) and to consider bringing multiple networks together to co-host meetings or hold adjacent annual meetings or conferences. A call was also made for more comparative work or synthesis projects to bring people together around extant data.

Bridging Alaskan & North Atlantic Arctic Research Agendas

US East Coast institutions involved in Arctic research have developed stronger regional ties through the establishment of the New England Arctic Network over the past few years. With the close proximity of these organizations to Greenland and the coupled North Atlantic-Arctic system, the national and international profile of this active regional community as a second US Arctic research gateway—distinct from Alaska—is growing.

In 2022, the University of Maine and University of Maine Southeast both became new members of the ARCUS consortium. Looking for ways to grow the institutional ties between these new members and ARCUS' Alaskan-based organizations, ARCUS Board Members raised the idea of formulating a shared Arctic research agenda that builds on the interests, assets, and capacities of both regions.

To explore the potential of this idea further, two ARCUS Board members—Dr. Pips Veazey from the University of Maine and Dr. Lauren Culler from Dartmouth College—led an Annual Meeting breakout discussion to help identify existing connections between Alaskan and North Atlantic-based Arctic research efforts, thematic similarities between the Arctic research interests of each region, and activities that could be undertaken to move the idea of developing a shared research agenda forward.

Examples of existing regional connections shared included:

- The Juneau Icefield Research Program (<https://juneauicefield.org/>) - this program is run primarily by the University of Maine with significant support from the University of Alaska Southeast.
- University of the Arctic thematic networks that engage researchers from both regions.
- Navigating the New Arctic projects with ties to both Alaska and New England.

- NSF Research Traineeships based at the University of Alaska Fairbanks ([Tamamta](#)), University of Maine ([SAUNNA](#)) and University of New Hampshire ([CARPE](#)) with supplemental funding to work together.
- The former IGERT on Polar Environmental Change (<http://www.igert.org/highlights/513.html>).
- Arctic Domain Awareness Center activities such as [Nancy Kinner's oil spill response work](#) and [ICECON](#).

A number of thematic research areas with relevance to both regions were discussed, including: security & disaster preparedness; health research; immigration & changing mobility patterns (e.g., increased vessel traffic & tourism); energy; marine affairs; physical environment comparisons & linkages; changing climate & the pan-Arctic effects of a warming environment; education, training, and advancement of new Arctic research cohorts; and social justice & reconciliation.

Similar to other Annual Meeting discussions focused on promoting greater alignment across established networks, discussants interested in developing these regional connections further echoed the desire for tools such as directories of subject matter experts, open repositories to better enable data and information sharing (including best practices for both working with communities and team science), and more social infrastructure to support networking across disciplines. A request was made for more workshops and meetings organized around specific themes, focused on developing societally relevant work, and capable of connecting with both communities and practitioners (e.g., industry & land managers) that live and operate in the Arctic. The group discussed the idea of establishing a research coordination network to further support information exchange and foster collaboration. The group also recognized the potential value of the regional East Coast and Alaskan research communities working together to engage with congressional delegates around Arctic-relevant policy issues.

III. NEXT STEPS

The ideas and suggestions generated during ARCUS Annual Meetings are used to inform strategic planning discussions among ARCUS staff, board members, and our funders and shape the future directions of ARCUS community activities and programs. ARCUS will establish committees and working groups in early 2023 to take action on ideas summarized in this report. Calls for ARCUS member participation in these groups will be announced through the ArcticInfo email list and ARCUS Monthly Report newsletter. We hope other organizations and individuals will also join us in using the ARCUS Annual Meeting discussions to inform the development of their own partnerships and strategies to address the needs of the Arctic research community.

PHOTO BY ERIN TOWNS (POLARTREC 2022)

IV. MEETING ORGANIZERS, DISCUSSION FACILITATORS, & PARTICIPANTS

ARCUS would like to thank our planning committee and breakout discussion facilitators for their time and thoughtful contributions to the 2022 ARCUS Annual Meeting agenda and small group discussions. Their efforts to make the Annual Meeting a valuable experience for the ARCUS community is sincerely appreciated!

Annual Meeting Planning Committee

Adrian Gall (ABR, Inc.)
 Stacey Fritz (National Renewable Energy Laboratory/
 CCHRC)
 Heather Sauyag Jean Gordon (Child Trends)
 Åsa Rennermalm (Rutgers University)
 Ming Xiao (Pennsylvania State University)
 Emily Maxwell (University of Alaska Anchorage)
 Helen Wiggins (ARCUS Executive Director)
 Brit Myers (ARCUS Engagement Director)

Breakout Discussion Facilitators***Exploring ARCUS Member Goals, Activities, & Expertise***

- Ming Xiao (US Permafrost Association) & Helen Wiggins (ARCUS)
- Adrian Gall (ABR, Inc.) & Stacey Stoudt (ARCUS)

Utilizing Indigenous Co-Production of Knowledge Frameworks & Supportive Practices

- Heather Sauyag Jean Gordon (Child Trends) & Åsa Rennermalm (Rutgers)
- Cana Uluak Itchuaqiyag (Virginia Tech) & Lisa Sheffield Guy (ARCUS)

Identifying Supports for International Collaborations

- Diane Hirshberg (University of Alaska Anchorage) & Gary Wilson (University of Northern British Columbia)
- Peter Webley (University of Alaska Fairbanks) & Betsy Turner-Bogren (ARCUS)

Promoting Alignment & Connections Across Arctic Research Networks

- Emily Maxwell (University of Alaska Anchorage) & Judy Fahnestock (ARCUS)
- Stacey Fritz (NREL/CCHRC) & Alexis Will (WWF US Arctic Program)

Bridging Alaskan & North Atlantic Arctic Research Agendas

- Pips Veazey (University of Maine) & Lauren Culler (Dartmouth University)

Individual Participants

To view a list of all 2022 ARCUS Annual Meeting participants, please visit:

https://www.arcus.org/files/meeting/attendees/arcus_2022annualmeeting_participants.pdf

Participating ARCUS Member Institutions

Alaska Ocean Observing System
 Arizona State University
 Dartmouth College
 Kawerak, Inc.
 National Renewable Energy Laboratory
 Norwegian Polar Institute
 Rutgers University
 Sandia National Laboratories
 Sitka Sound Science Center
 Texas A&M University
 The George Washington University
 U.S. Permafrost Association
 University of Alaska Anchorage
 University of Alaska Fairbanks
 University of Alaska Southeast
 University of Lapland, Arctic Centre
 University of Maine
 University of Northern British Columbia
 University of Southern Maine
 University of the Arctic
 University of Virginia
 University of Washington
 Woodwell Climate Research Center
 World Wildlife Fund, U.S. Arctic Program

Appendix: Meeting Agenda & Themes & Questions for Small Group Conversations: https://www.arcus.org/files/meetings/agendas/arcus_2022_annual_meeting_agenda_version_23_september_2022.pdf

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